

USE OF THE KURDISH LOCAL LANGUAGE HAS CONTRIBUTED TO POOR PROFICIENCY AND PERFORMANCE AMONG THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS IN AMEDIYA DISTRICT IRAQ

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ABSTRACT

The Kurdistan region of Iraq achieved autonomy in 1991 which resulted in Indo-European and Kurdish people developing a positive attitude towards using and teaching the English language. Especially in the education system, some reforms were put in place including setting new policies in education, setting new curricula and establishing new schools. To enhance the knowledge of the Kurdish EFL student's communicative language teaching an English program called Sunrise was started. The researcher focused on investigating on use of local language in teaching English as a key cause of student's failure. The researcher feels that in the study area the English Sunrise program does not meet the need of the students due some factors such as poor infrastructure, lack of enough English teacher training, poor communicative activities. With good command of English the students will be capable of passing and pursuing best courses such as medicine and engineering among others. Having professionals and academic materials available in the Kurdish language has highly caused a problem for students learning English their second language. The Kurdish learners don't care about speaking skills since the examinations are multiple choices. Another fact is that English is spoken by very few people in the study area thus making many students have less interest in studying this language. The teachers are not successful English speakers, and also majority have a bachelor's degree.

Keywords: Kurdistan region of Iraq (KRI), Kurdish community, EFL program, approaches of language teaching and teaching English

Background Information

The fact that English is a global language has made non-English speaking nations consider and use it as necessary for non-English speakers to start acquiring the English language. Anyone mastering English will have a guarantee to be successful in the job market and class work as well. There is the essence of the Kurdish students to familiarize themselves with the English language and acquire the proper communication skills as this will make them successful in academics. The researchers identified that KRI English language program is being faced by many challenges which contribute to the poor performance of the Kurdish learners.

The Kurdish language is a branch of the median language referred as old Iran language. Kurdistan is a region that borders Iran, Syria, Turkey, and Iraq where we have an Indo European group called Kurds. They are among the largest ethnic groups in Iraq and turkey; we also have others in Lebanon, Afghanistan, Turkmenistan, Armenia, and Azerbaijan. In 1932 the Kurds in Iraq became independent. Although up to 1958 it was under British control. The British were causing instability to Kurdish independence since it did not support Kurdish independence. This resulted to uprisings in 199

Problem statement

Learning English through in the KRI environment has resulted in poor outcomes and little achievements of the students in all levels of education. In the study area, the use of unsuitable English program that is Sunrise has poor presentation style, cultural contest and inappropriate communicative activities. Inadequate time allocated to teachers make them unable to complete the syllabus, inadequate English teaching equipment's and infrastructure and having a large size of the class has been another problem since using of communicative language teaching approach is not applicable.

Lack of incentives and proper training to teachers and inadequate English professionals has been a major problem. Use of local Kurdish language in teaching has made students develop negative interest in learning English, and thus they lack communication skills since they learn to pass the multiple choices examination. There is thus a need for the students to advise that learning English and becoming mastery in English will open doors for their future careers.

1.3 Purpose of the study

The study aimed at analyzing how the use of the Kurdish local language has contributed to poor proficiency and performance among the English language learners in Amediya district. This researcher believed this resulted in students performing poorly in English in KRI context. Not many students in public schools irrespective of their level of education can communicate effectively in English. This is a matter of concerns since many students are underperforming.

The poor results are recorded by students as a result of having social and administrative aspects. Unqualified teachers and use of local Kurdish language in teaching this subject is a key challenge. Students need to be provided with quality education to enable them to be proficient in the English language.

The needs of the learners are not fully satisfied by the syllabus Sunrise program. And there for the poor curriculum of English teachers colleges fail to equip them with a relevant course based on English language teaching method and thus no enough trained teachers. The research is analyzing how the KRI education system is affected by social cultural and educational constraints as determinants hindering the learner and English teacher development (Vernez et al,2014).

As of now, the main challenges include the use of Kurdish local language in teaching other subjects, increase in need for education, having overcrowded classrooms, poor quality education provided by teachers, short class sessions, the poor performance of students in KRI national tests, lack of incentives and accountability. The researcher believes that if there is effective English language teaching approach instead of Kurdistan local language in teaching English learners, The English program will effectively attain its goals and make the Kurdish English students master in English and become fluent English speakers (Avci, & Doghonadze, 2017).

1.4 General objective

To identify the determinants of poor performance of English learners in KRI national standardized tests
Objectives of the study

1. To identify how the use of Kurdish local language has contributed to poor performance of English learners
2. To assess how the use of unsuitable English program has contributed to student's failure
3. To identify the challenges facing the English teachers and how they contribute to students failure

1.5 Research questions

This study aimed at answering the following research questions

1. How does the use of Kurdish local language influence the performance of English learners in KRI?
2. How does the use of unsuitable English program affect the students' performance?
3. How do the challenges facing English teachers in KRI contribute towards students' poor

performance?

1.6 The significance of the study

This project presents a better understanding of the targeted audience in learning English as a second language, and their views on the rules policies and regulations set for the same. This, in turn, will help the ministry of education, the administration of the public schools, the students, the teachers as well as the Kurdish community, to consider better policy formulation and implementation approaches in teaching the English language in KRI. The findings help the relevant stakeholders in the ministry of education, the teacher's service commission, and other parties with interest in supporting English as a second language to prioritize their management plans and projects accordingly putting regard the needs and the interest of both the students and teachers.

**2:0 CHAPTER TWO
LITERATURE REVIEW****2.1 Introduction****2.2 Societal factors impact language teaching philosophy.**

The philosophy of teaching language is impacted by the societal aspects which include the Policymakers, such as government, political leaders, parents, students and teachers among others. From the time Kurdish attained independence the Kurdish language and Arabic are used as official languages in KRI. There are two dialects in Kurdish Sorani and Kurmanji; they use a different alphabet (Vernez et al,2014)..

The big challenge with the language learning comes to Kurdish learner who must have to study the native dialect, different from the Kurdish language, Arabic, and English dialect. Generally, in KRI a lot of time is used on languages since it is clear that there is a need for enough time for Multilanguage instruction and appropriate material and effective language teachers are needed.

According to research done by Norton 2012 in KRI, the education system has some challenges as it targets Multilanguage teaching. Since Kurdish English learners tend to hope for the best in attaining the best communication and skills, they in return have unachievable goals due to poor services provided poor teaching approaches.

A research done by (Rizi et al,2014) on Deficiencies associated with learning and teaching English as a second language in secondary schools shows that in Iran and India English learners are negatively affected by the se of local language .To explain on that view the English program in KRI education has been impeded by lack of focus on multiple languages and inadequate enforcement of key approaches of language teaching including, the material used in teaching, students' needs, language tutor targets and effective evaluation among others. It is very true that the Sunrise as the EFL program does not meet its key objectives based on various reasons like inappropriate textbooks, poor teacher training, overcrowded class and social backgrounds among other reasons.

According to Lie 2017, there is no way that the syllabus will be well covered and delivered effectively to a class of over 40 students irrespective of how the curriculum is excellent. Researchers highlight that reduction of the class size will result in improvements of the English learners.

2.3 Use of prescribed course in Kurdistan Regional education curricula

Generally, the Kurdistan region public school teachers follow the already prescribed course that is the Sunrise program which the ministry of education has approved a fit. Because teachers in this region are not well paid they do teaching career as a part-time job. This makes the teachers have a side hustle like starting and business which can make them have a decent living; It will, therefore, result to them not having enough time to develop themselves professionally as well as limiting their time to prepare well for instructions. Therefore causing they deliver poor quality education, Research by Pennington and Richards 2008 shows that there is need of supporting the novice English teachers and guiding them since they are somehow can fail to use communicative perspective when teaching just like what they were doing in training institutes. Like using an approach that lacks involvement of leaners like teacher-centered approach.

Avci, & Doghonadze, (2017) identified that the KRI most of the teaching staff is lacking strong skills in English causing them to perform poorly .this is associated with the teachers being poorly trained. Involvement and inclusion of teachers in the development of curricula instead of complaining and see the only negative part of them in students' performance.

2.4 School Capacity and Double Shift Schools

There is the possibility of Kurdish children having the advantage of acquiring English through natural way based on the fact that it is taught from the first grade in basic KRI education system. There is a challenge that is observed since in the use of double and multiple shift schools in the current education system. Schools that are administered in a double shift in the daily program and others tend to share their building with other schools which could result in a lack of basic needs like electricity and water (Al-Hamash, 2013).

The above deficiencies tend to result in social-cultural factors which affect the process of English teaching and education. Lamb 2012 found that in Indonesia the students coming from rural areas do not trust in themselves whether they will become proficient English speakers in future (Norton, 2012).

Additionally, students coming from a low-income family have little trust in themselves in academic achievement.

A researcher conducted by Nikolov in Hungary points out that the family level of education determines how students learn and perform in English learning. A similar researcher did in Europe has shown that students from educated family members were more proficient in speaking English and performed well in English tests (Avci, & Doghonadze, 2017).

In conjunction with this in KRI context, the students coming from rural areas tend to have challenges in accessing city libraries, private schools where they can easily make improvements on their communication. The English novice teachers are the ones who are given the duty by the ministry of education to teach in the rural areas for some period before they move to cities (Mahboob & Elyas, 2014).

2.5 Teacher students' relationship

A researcher done by Freeman 2008 shows that the teacher-student relationship is determined by the social-cultural context. Additionally, Kurdish English students do not have the freedom to decide what they should be taught and how they want it to be taught.

It is, therefore, true that Kurdish English learners will miss developing English acquisition if instructional approach above is used which won't make English students improve their communication skills (Avci, & Doghonadze, 2017).

Another point of concern is that the materials used in teaching English fail to reflect the needs of the learner. There is a need for interaction between the teacher and students this will enable the teachers to understand the strengths of the students as well as their weakness (Hassan, 2014).

Brown 2010 argues that students acquiring English as the second language should be having positive experiences. Since lack of interest towards English will lower the learner motivation making them less successful. Lastly, he argued that English teachers should always be learning facilitator's as this will make them very useful and motivating to the students.

2.7 Education and School Structure in KRI

Decision making and administration are centralized in Kurdistan regional government, and independent ministry of education. We have 12 directorates in KRI, and KRG ministry of education is play role in managing curriculum, generating tests, employing and posting teachers to schools, it also determines strategies for teacher and principles and establishing and renovating schools. Additionally both principal and teachers autonomy do not enable them to make any decision or policy this leaves a gap since they are key stakeholders in the ministry of educations.

Principle do not have adequate mandate to be an instructional leader as it was highlighted by Vernez et al in 2014, they have little responsibilities in the assessment of the performance of the teachers and no role in guiding them on the method of teaching. This cause a major challenge for Kurdish English learners and their teachers too. The key stakeholder where the English language program will be done should instead have the inclusion of all stakeholders communicating, forming relationships, and making decisions together to enhance positive changes in the education sector (Abdul-Kareem, 2009).

Research conducted by Morris on the USA explains that having interaction setting will give favorite or ethos encouraging change and implementing innovations. This can only be achieved in a school where there is good cooperation between the principal and the other teachers

2.8 The English program Sunrise and the English teachers in KRI

A research done by Ebadi, & Hasan, (2016). Shows that it is hard for an English teacher to make use of the new teaching policy and use communicative language teaching as well as a student-based approach as it is in the education reform. The English teacher will face challenges to perform such duties in a class that has many students such as 40 when using the materials like markers, CDs, and textbooks.

Students can't be able to access electricity to enable them to use CD since they sit packed it is, therefore, important to use new technologies such as projectors and internet to enhance communication. There is a need for coming up with different class environment away from the other subjects, this will enhance extensive English exposure for the pupils so that they can have enough experience in the English language (Ebadi & Hasan, 2016).

If the class is overcrowded, the English teacher will have a lot of time wasted in instructional time on managing and controlling the class. Generally, we can say that the teacher will eventually have no option rather than using teacher-centered approach because there is improper seating arrangement of the students, inadequate activities and space for moving around as well as lack of time which are key contributors to the poor quality of

English teaching forces. According to researchers use of this approach will only ensure that few students are in actual language learning and additionally students are only provided with knowledge about language but not motivated on how to use it purposely (Ebadi & Hasan, 2016).

2.9 Language Policy in KRI

Richards 2011 explains that teaching a foreign language is standard practice in many nations. Though the roles played by foreign language changes from one state to another, depending on the curriculum, the experience of teaching , attitude education traditions as well as the expectation of teaching a foreign language, In Netherlands, the language policy calls for the teaching of one or many foreign languages in the education curricula. In America, there is literature centered teaching approach although teaching foreign language in this country is not required (Rizi et al,2014).

2.10 Teachers and Teacher Training in KRI

In his article, Miller 2007 on the responsibility of English language tutors in English language education, tries to alert on the significance of the role played by tutors in the learning a language. The researchers wanted to identify the qualities of successful English teachers. He explains the effectiveness of the EFL teacher passion for teaching which can keep the learners motivated as well as preparing them to be ready for the lesson. Creativity in teaching ensures that tutors do not only follow the textbook. Progress in learning language will be witnessed if the students are not afraid to make mistakes there for a good teacher will have to add skillful humor to the class (Hassan, 2014). The researchers also pointed out that teachers showing interest with the students will be effective English teachers it is good to challenge the students by speaking in English and waiting for them to respond in English this will enhance their communication skills. Miller urges that patient and teacher who can persevere with students will contribute to positive results to them and make the English learners successful (Vernez et al,2014).

2.11 Time Influence in Students' Achievement

Increasing the time used in instructional programs will contribute to improvement in academic achievement. The student learning is expanded by increasing the time a teacher spends teaching this gives the student unlimited opportunities to consult and ask questions. Kurdish English lack adequate time to cover the syllabus during an academic year. The Kurdish English teachers have had minimum time to cover their syllabus during the academic year. Inadequate school facilities in KRI also contribute to hindering teachers form delivering excellent English teaching. For instance, in 40 to 50 minutes a class of 40 to 50 students cannot be given an opportunity for each student to speak like this will take a lot of time (Ebadi & Hasan, 2016).

2.12 knowledge gap

High expectation of the ministry of education and other stakeholders on the benefits of teaching English as a foreign language in public schools, remain being challenged by the fact that there are institutional arrangements that are not well managed while some of the current frameworks and programs in the curriculum were formed without regards to students and teachers' needs. There is still a knowledge gap in teaching the English language in KRI on the extent the students are allowed to use the local language while learning English as a second language. This is because there are scenarios where the rich in the community are able to pay for their children English in private schools. The focus on the challenges facing the teachers is a reflection on how teachers struggle to give their best, a gap remain in establishing the exact manner in which the ministry of education will develop the perfect curriculum where learning a foreign language can achieve their needs. Previous researches have shown that the poor programs are used in teaching English as a foreign language, on top of these the poor take their students to public schools to learn foreign languages but it comes out that only the students from the rich families acquire the skills from private schools. In order for the community to fully benefit from the English language in KRI, there is need to deeply understand the interest of the students and teachers and mainstream them in setting strategies on how to teach this subject. The research therefore aimed at best ways to close the existing gap in using local language while teaching English as a second language in KRI.

**3:0 CHAPER THREE
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY****3.1 Introduction**

This chapter gives a descriptions of the research design applied; target population, sample size and sampling procedures to be used in the actual research

3.2 Research Design

This study was based on a detailed survey to capture descriptive data from selected samples in the descriptive survey approach, correlation design is considered since there is interaction with different groups of people, to understand the processes, conditions, practices, and structures of the outcome of this research.

3.3 Target Population

The target population for this study was both the Kurdish people and into European group in the society who strongly understand the education system of KRI. To get the adequate sample size for this study, the researcher used a sample size of 25 individuals both teachers and students from Amediya district.

3.4: Sampling Technique

Multi-stage cluster sampling was used to arrive at those included in the survey for an interview. The target stakeholders, Kurdish leaders, EFL TEACHERS, and community members both literate and illiterate are included in the study.

3.5 Research Instruments

Data was collected using a structured questionnaire, specifically designed for this study, consisting of four sections. The questionnaires self-administered questionnaires. Research assistants were employed to assist in the administration of questionnaires and processing.

3.6 Data Collection Procedures

The method to collect the data in selected students from different public schools in Amediya district the Local Council (LCs) officers were briefed, who later introduced researcher to village chiefs who approved, and recognition letter was given so that the researcher continues with research in the selected localities. Questionnaires were administered with the help of research assistants to the respondents and in every evening checked for completeness and accuracy.

3.7 Data Processing

Both secondary and primary techniques of data collection were viable and applicable to the dissertation; therefore, the study made use of information sources such as libraries and relevant sources of information

3.8 Data Analysis and Presentation

After data collection, they were organized and analyzed based on study guidelines. The analysis of data from the respondent's expressions, perceptions, events, questionnaires, behavioral observation, maps, and records. Arrays of techniques were employed for site analysis and presentation. They include both descriptive and qualitative techniques. In the descriptive analysis, proportions, percentages averages were used to arrive at a general picture upon which conclusion was made(Vernez et al,2014)..

Qualitative methods used include statistical tables and bar graphs which were done using Microsoft Excel software. Successful analysis of data entailed Sorting data: organizing both coded and random data into categories that best serve the purpose of the study. It also entails prioritizing information based on relevancy and reliability (Salisbury,2004). Quality control check: this is a control strategy in research that ensures all data collected are important and relevant. In many circumstances, research without quality control systems has flaws that subject them to many questions.

**4:0 CHAPTER FOUR
DATA ANALYSIS PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION**

Figure 1: Electricity acces in schools in the KRI, by Sub-District 2017-2018
Source: MOE statistis 2017-2018

From the respondents it is clear that overcrowded classes the English teacher will have a lot of time wasted in instructional time on managing and controlling the class.

schools without acces to electricity will not be able to use projectors ,CDs and other teaching materials used in teaching the English language as it was clarified by the respondents it is very clear that these limits teachers to use teacher-based approach while delivering their instruction. (Avci, & Doghonadze, 2017).

Figure 2 Education Level of KRI Teachers, by Grades and Total, 2017-18

Source: MOE statistics, 2017-18

It is advised that English teachers to be knowledgeable at grammar as this will reflect their performance, being available is another strength that will enhance the teachers student relationship, lastly the researcher explains that there should be equal treatment of all students as well as these help to point out the areas where teacher role can positively or negatively affect the students performance (Harmandaoglu Baz,2018).

Figure 3 Teachers specialization in academics, 2007-08

Source: MOE data 2017-18.

From the above table it is very clear that there are other subjects that the teachers can also specialize in or teach and if students lose become demotivated by learning English since there is so many teachers offering services in the Kurdish language and Arabic languages which are alternatives of the English language and more common in the region than the foreign language. In conjunction to these data, it can be concluded that Kurdish local language is applied in the system of education and lack of motives and accountability in teaching the English language in KRI might result to a big challenge in future (Avci, & Doghonadze,

2017).

Figure 4 Percentage of Teachers preparation

Source: MOE teacher Survey 2017

From the above presentation, it is clear that the majority of the teachers do not have enough time during the instructional period thought the academic year. Those using the content of new curricula are the leading with 48%. Followed closely by teachers who apply student based instructional approaches at 42%, closely there are other approaches such as changing the scope of the curriculum at 38% and these using new curriculum materials at 36%.

From the respondents, it is true that considering the School Capacity and Double Shift Schools the average class size is 35 pupils and 45 percent of the classes are overcrowded. From the respondents, it is clear that a teacher can have a hard time in managing a class of over 35 students and cannot be able to use other approaches which enhance communication skills.

Figure 5 overcrowding in school based on Grade Level and urbanity 2017-18
Source: MoE Statistics School Data, 2017-18

5:0 CHAPTER FIVE**SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS****5.1 Summary of findings**

The researcher sought to identify whether the use of the Kurdish language affects the Kurdish English learner's performance in academics. From the respondents it is very clear that many of the local people have little or no interest in learning English as a foreign language, the researcher could thereby conclude that the use of societal factors highly influences language teaching philosophy.

Additionally, from the respondents in the study area, it is very clear that Kurdish people have a negative perception on learning English due to the fact that the ministry of education uses a prescribed course in KRI which is not meeting the students' needs and does not enhance communication skills. Another observation that was made is that there are many schools that have double shifts which pressurize the teachers and English learners due to the time wasted when relocation g to new lecture venues. The researchers also could conclude that the people from the study area complained of lack of enough and appropriate teacher-student relationship which is caused by overcrowded class sizes and thus making some of the students fails to get or consult on what was taught. There is need to set a good an inappropriate education an school structure in which might change the motivation of both the teachers and learners to change the attitude in teaching or learning English as a second language. The respondent also made it clear that use of English sundries by the English teachers does not necessarily meet the students need some need proper attention and creative teachers to help them understand the concepts.

Many of the respondents especially the teachers claimed that they have not received adequate training or do not get seminars o and training during the academic years which could bring new ideas and opinions. Lastly it is very clear that the teachers in this region do not receive good salary which could sustain them and make them have decent living this makes them start investments and work as part times in school, this has negative impact to the students due to the fact that they will lack time to prepare well with course and thus influencing their performance.

The research explored numerous challenges that influence teaching English dialect in the KRI These limitations mostly show themselves in instructor school syllabi, instructor training, course readings, class congestion, and physical foundations. It is suggested recommendations to fortify ELT in KRI. Additionally, Congestion in the KRI's Schools English language instructors in KRI has obligations and undertakings that are difficult to achieve in the congested classes. This inescapably displays challenges for English instructors. They cannot furnish learners with opinions in such situations. Time cannot be committed to every scholar to assess dialect aptitudes and address personal prerequisites. The additional time learners are occupied with dialect learning, the more dialect is contributed. Self-awareness influences inspiration, disposition, and nervousness. An English educator will not have the capacity to give enough consideration regarding every learner to work together (Hassan, 2014).

5.2 Recommendation

English dialect teachers will perform better and viable in small classes employing efficient English dialect teaching techniques and methodologies, (Vernez et al,2014).

Setting up educator guidance centers affiliated with English educator schools where full-time and expert English dialect mentors offer exhaustive and reliable courses on teaching techniques and strategies enabled by institutionalized training materials.

Enlist full-time proficient EFL mentors from the locality and worldwide instructor schools to guarantee that English educator preparing is occurring in a reliable way over the KRI (Kavlu,2015).

Provision of a broad focal point on instructional method training, applying institutionalized preparation materials that focus on training techniques and attitudes that will prepare English instructors to effectively adjust and outline their own particular materials and communicative exercises (Brown,2001).

Local subjects that intrigue learners: engaging themes can be addressed to meet the requisites and interests of the students hence influencing and identifying with apprentices lives. Worldwide topics and societies which upgrade English students' competency of semantic components, soberly minded components, and suprasegmentally components of elocution (Freeman, 2008).These capabilities help ELLs to utilize English suitably in different social associations with an abnormal state of lucidity, clarity, and appreciation Learning through self-think about, self-instruction, or separation learning does not infer having self-rule in learning. Along these lines, learning without anyone else's input does not mean having abilities and ability to learn independently from anyone else.

5.3 Conclusion

Generally, the researcher was concluded that the use of local dialect highly affects the performance of both English learners and the EFL teachers in KRI. This has contributed to student's failure in KRI because it leaves Kurdish English students unequipped.

It is also clear that use of Kurdish local language has contributed to poor performance of English learners and use of unsuitable English program has contributed to students' failure. The research also concludes that poor quality services by English teachers can be as a result of challenges facing the English teachers this contribute to students failure in exams.

5.4 Suggestion for further research

Concisely, breaking down training and English as a second language in KRI's setting may require more research to identify if the use of local dialect might have a positive contribution towards teaching and learning English as second language KRI. Reach should be done also to identify which another alternative foreign language can be taught easily in KRI to the Kurdish people. Through this, we will be able to improve the English program in KRI's specific situation, by taking a few measures that include constructing new schools, planning another educational module, advancing an educator preparing framework, redesigning English courses in instructor universities, enlisting exceedingly competent English instructors and mentors, lack of enough and appropriate teacher-student relationship which is caused by overcrowded class sizes and thus making some of the students fails to get or consult on what was taught. There is need to set a good an inappropriate education an school structure in which might change the motivation of both the teachers and learners to change the attitude in teaching or learning English as a second language. The respondent also made it clear that the use of English sundries by the English teachers does not necessarily meet the students need some need proper attention and creative teachers to help them understand the concepts.

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6:0 Appendix

6.1 Map of the study area

Figure 6 Kurdistan region Iraq